

THE PROBLEM OF EQUIVALENCE OF EUPHEMISMS

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ABSTRACT

The media, in particular, the press, is the main source of information about the situation in the world today, about the events that are taking place in it, and in many cases includes "negative" news. In order to soften or obliterate information, which has a negative nature, which is presented by the media, indirect means of re-naming in the press-euphemisms are used. The problem of adequacy and equivalence of translation is one of the pressing problems of modern translation studies. One of the main tasks of the translator is to convey the content of the original as completely as possible, and, as a rule, the actual similarity of the content of the original and the translation is very significant.

Introduction.

Translation activity is a complex creative activity based on many different factors: linguistic, cultural and socio-communicative, which constantly necessarily causes the need for its scientific understanding. Being an interdisciplinary field of knowledge, translation studies as a scientific discipline combining the humanities of text linguistics, stylistics, semiotics, comparative linguistics, linguoculturology, primarily solves the issue that affects both the definition of the translation process itself and the characteristics of the criteria for its implementation and evaluation. Translators know from their own experience how difficult it is sometimes to accurately recreate the semantic content of both a separate "unit of thought" (for

example, expressed by a phrase) and the entire thought (contained in a sentence). It is very important for a translator to know about the peculiarities of the use of euphemisms in the language in order to correctly assess the role of the subtext, especially when translating journalistic materials or fiction.

Main part.

The word, being subjected to various implementations in the act of communication, thereby manifests its social and communicative function. As a result of the spread and impact of mass media and various psychological pressures on the language, new formations such as euphemisms are now intensively penetrating into all spheres of spoken and literary language. Euphemistic tendencies in English have spread especially strongly

in the USA. Therefore, some American linguists even suggest distinguishing between two languages - the "language of facts" (fact language) and the "language of ideas" (idea language), and the latter, in their opinion, may well be used for purposes contrary to the true nature of communications: not to express thought, but to mask it. Researcher J. Wagner points out that when a person, for example, endlessly hears (or reads) phrases that communicate information such as: Coca-Cola refreshes you best - Coca-Cola is the best refreshing drink, that is, information that is far from the actual state of things, as a result, the meaning of the phrase collapses. And this, in turn, leads to the fact, states J. Wagner, that many Americans are gradually losing faith in language, becoming convinced that "words are unreliable" (words are tricky) [citation 31].

According to A.V. Kunin, euphemism is a phenomenon of a "broad social order". "Euphemism," writes A.V. Kunin, "is resorted to wherever it is necessary to disguise, soften, weaken a particular word or expression" [33, p.16] Euphemisms are especially widely used in advertising language, in slang and in professional jargon (shop talk).

For example, *pawnshops* (pawnshops) are now increasingly referred to in advertisements in the United States not as shops, but as jewelry companies and loan and jewelry companies. The *guitarist* prefers to call himself not a guitarist, but a recording artist; entertainer; singer, known only for performances in a number of local or private clubs, offering his "services, for example, to the theater, speaks of himself as a pop artist (showman, entertainer, performer). Previously *used cars* for many years in the USA were simply called used

cars or second-hand cars, but now old cars are increasingly advertised not as previously used (used cars), but as cars previously owned (pre-owned cars). In accordance with this kind of advertising, a special euphemistic language penetrates literally into all areas of life. So, in order not to call a spade a spade, mentioning the market on American stock exchanges, they no longer say a *recession* (fall), but a lull in business operations (easing) or, as Wall Street brokers say, there is an adjustment of the stock price (correction is made) or a reconfiguration (adjustment, technical correction). *Technical adjustment* (correction) occurs when there is a decline in the stock price on the stock exchange, and not an increase. In order to avoid words that paint a depressing picture of the state of the capitalist economy, so as not to use such, for example, a concept as 'chronic inflation' (chronic inflation), some economists "correct" the state of economic affairs by using a euphemism - a synonym for the word inflation - gradual increase in prices and wages.

The stock market boom, as you know, is often accompanied by a sharp depression (depression, bust); in order not to use such words, the euphemism business cycle was invented - the cycle of business activity. Even the traditional economic concept of supply and demand is increasingly being replaced by such an abstract-sounding term as regulated prices and wages (administered prices and wages) [31].

The poor (the poor) in the economic press turned into the very needy (the neediest), then simply into the needy (the needy, the ill-provided), then into people deprived of benefits (the deprived), then into the socially deprived (the socially

deprived), then into the underprivileged (the underprivileged), and later into those who fell into less favorable life circumstances (the disadvantaged) and, finally, into the low-income (low-income people).

Unjustified use of euphemisms in some cases (in the field of classification of professions, etc.) leads to the use of very unusual words-names in the English language. A number of examples are given below:

Existing names	Definition	Encountered new names	Definition
boarding house	<i>A lodging house at which meals are provided</i>	guest house (Br.)	<i>A house run as a bed-and-breakfast</i>
beauty-shop operator	<i>One that operates in beauty parlour</i>	beautician	<i>A person licensed to provide cosmetic treatments to the hair, skin, and nails</i>
garbage collector	<i>One who collects and hauls away garbage</i>	sanitation engineer	<i>someone who removes waste material th at people put outside their houses</i>
rat-catcher	<i>One who puts traps for rats</i>	extermination engineer	<i>to kill large numbers of rats that they no longer exist</i>
dog-catcher	<i>a <u>dog warden</u></i>	animal welfare officer	<i>One who provides care for animals without owner</i>
fire	<i>to force someone to leave their job</i>	remove	<i>To dismiss someone from a job</i>
stool pigeon	<i>someone, especially a criminal, who helps the police to catch another criminal, usually by giving them information</i>	police informant	<i>someone who secretly gives the police, the army etc information about someone else</i>
janitor	<i>someone whose job is to look after a school or other large building</i>	custodian	<i>someone who is responsible for looking after something important or valuable</i>

From the examples given, it can be seen that euphemisms are a very complex and contradictory phenomenon in the language. In some cases, their use seems quite legitimate. So, in fiction, euphemisms are an effective stylistic tool for writers who resort to it in order to revive the language of characters. In many cases, euphemisms are perhaps appropriate in

medicine, sometimes quite possible in the language of modern diplomacy.

On the other hand, when euphemisms are adopted by individual masters of advertising, this, according to W. Safayer [54], leads to the fact that many phrases-slogans and words turn out to be incomprehensible even for native English speakers themselves. Stereotyped thinking, ideologized and metaphorical speech and

other features of the language make it very difficult to adequately translate emotionally-evaluative and stylistically colored vocabulary. This vocabulary, saturated with figurative expressions reflecting the views of certain social groups, is closely connected with the corresponding linguistic and cultural environment, and an adequate perception of this vocabulary by representatives of another linguistic and cultural group is often impossible without knowledge and understanding of linguistic and cultural differences between these groups.

Hence the conclusion for the translator: it is necessary to assimilate not only the main meaning of the word, but also secondary meanings, which are just realized in various speech situations. The emphasis should be placed on the assimilation of the entire range of meanings of a word or a word-concept, and

then none of the meanings and none of the shades of thought will escape the attention of the translator.

Conclusion. The translation of euphemisms is impossible without taking into account background information (the specific political content of the events described in the text) and the linguistic and cultural background. The translation of euphemisms is context-dependent, when translating the same lexemes, depending on the context and background information, different interpretations can be given. Obstacles and difficulties in the process of adequate translation of euphemisms can be overcome by harmonizing the political thesaurus of the original language and the language of translation. The most acceptable methods of translating euphemisms are the method of addition and the method of concretization.

REFERENCES:

1. Usmonova, Z. H., & Fayziyeva, A. A. (2019). LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL PECULIARITIES OF COMPLEX TERMS IN ISAAC ASIMOV'S WORKS. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 257-262.
2. Nafisa K. Cognition and Communication in the Light of the New Paradigm //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 214-217.
3. Firuza, N. (2021). Polysemy and its types in the non-related languages. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 12, 529-533.
4. Mehmonova Yulduz. Article expression of indefiniteness meaning in English and Uzbek languages. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional research* 10 (10) 345-349,2021.
5. Babaev Mahmud Tashpulatovich USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, VOLUME 12 May 2021. 64-67.
6. Olimova D. Z (2020) The effectiveness of implementation of ICT in learning process . *European Scholar Journal (ESJ)* Vol.1 No. 4. Pp. 9-11.
7. Khamroyevna, K. L. (2021). The Analysis of Education System in Uzbekistan: Challenges, Solutions and Statistical Analysis. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 9, 90-94.
8. G'ayratovna, R. . M. . (2021). Semantics of euphemistic and dysphemic units. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 12, 243-246.

9. Ruziyeva Nilufar Xafizovna (2021). The category of politeness in different linguocultural traditions. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL* 11 (2), 1667-1675
10. Khaydarova Nodirabegim Ahtamjonovna. (2021). Significance of Phraseological Units application in Medical Discourse of English and Uzbek Language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 11.
11. MUXTOROVA, M. (2022). OZBEK SHE'RIYATINING INGLIZCHA OGIRMALARIDA VATANPARVARLIK GOYASI IFODASIDA SOZ TANLASH MUAMMOSI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8).
12. Shakhnoza T. Binary Construction in the Speech // *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 210-213.
13. Ramazonovna T. S. On binary structured speech products in french // *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 10. – С. 381-386.
14. Imamkulova, Sitora. "The Intensity of Word Meanings." *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION* 1.2 (2021): 227-229.
15. Рабиева, М. (2021). Дихотомия эвфемизма и фразеологизма: Дихотомия эвфемизма и фразеологизма. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 7(7).
16. Bakhtiyorovna, I. F. . (2021). Translation of linguocultural peculiarities in hafiza kochkarova's translations. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 12, 247-249.
17. RADJABOV, R. R., & TOSHPULATOVA, N. (2021, March). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL VIEWS ON VITICULTURE AND ITS ROLE IN THE WORLD COMMUNITY. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 23-27).
18. Sobirovich, S. R. (2021). Ethymological Doublets Between French Verbs And Their Use. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 13.
19. Imamkulova Sitora Anvarovna. (2021). Cognitive Interpretation of Degrees of Intensification. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 11(1).